

THE ASSEMBLY AND THE EXPLOITATION OF THE CHRISTMAS TREES

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ABSTRACT

The article provides detailed information about the installation and exploitation of the Christmas trees installed at the mouth of the oil wells. The Christmas tree, which is the main part of the armature, assembled according to standard schemes at the factory or at the industrial manufactory, and after test for hermeticity, and as assembled delivered to the well. During the checking the following technological operations are performed.

The rotation of the valve flywheel performed without using a long arm.

Keywords: Christmas tree, flow line, valve, flange connection, tree, tee connector, buffer, hermeticity, spindle, well exploitation.

Formulation of the problem. The collection or installation of fountain and compressor fittings is carried out according to standard schemes. The collection of the fountain tree must be carried out at a factory or in a field workshop, pass a leak test, that is, compaction, and be delivered to the well in full assembly.

When introducing a column head, a final seal test must be verified.

In addition to tests of the Christmas tree, carried out at the factory or in the field workshop, before installation in the well to check the complete tightness and operation of connections and valves, the Christmas tree is subjected to additional testing.

To check the connections for leaks, perform the following operations:

- close the lower main and outer side valves on the discharge lines;
- fill the tree with water, at low temperatures with light oil;
- carry out pressure testing of the tree for test pressure from the holes for the pressure gauge installed on the buffer;
- hold the tree under pressure for 15 minutes.
- the flange bolts are secured with a hand wrench, first lightly and then forcefully; this is done in the direction of the cross;- при проверке задвижек их открывают, и снова закрывают до отказа [1,2,3].

If the pressure drops, it is necessary to identify the location of the leak and eliminate the defect by additionally reducing the pressure. After the second leak test, if the same defects are detected again, these parts must be replaced with new ones.

From the passage of the fountain fittings there should be an assembled template 2 meters long and with a diameter 2 mm smaller than the flow area of the tree trunk. The inner diameter of the tree trunk must be larger than the inner diameter of the riser pipes [2].

When connecting flanges with metal gaskets, additional cleaning of the flange surfaces and annular grooves is necessary, then install the gaskets. After placing the gaskets, the connecting flanges must be installed on top of each other so that the holes are installed using bolts. Additionally, you need to install several bolts on the flange hole. After the flange is seated, you need to put all the other bolts in place and tighten the nuts.

At first, the bolts are not tightly tightened with a wrench, and the fastening should be directed towards the crosspiece (diagonally). After this, you need to secure it with a special wrench with a handle 0.6-0.9 m long. The final fastening is carried out by stretching all the bolts sequentially. In this case, it is necessary to use bolts made of a special grade of factory-made steel.

Before installation, valves must undergo strict testing and inspection for closing and opening. Therefore you need to do the following: - исправность резьбы;

- accuracy of the pointer;
- in the case where there is no indicator above the valve for the complete opening and closing of the valve, check the accuracy of the number of periods.

The valves are checked in the following way. The valve opens completely and closes completely. In an open valve, the ram (shield) should not move to the flow area, and the indicator should indicate that the valve is completely open. When the valve is closed, the shield should fit tightly into its seat and the indicator should indicate that it is fully closed. If there is no indicator on the valve, then before hydraulic testing of the valve the exact amount of the lever period from the full open position to the closing of the valve must be determined and must be clearly indicated on the body.

Fig.1. Christmas tree diagrams according to GOST 13846-84 (№№ 1- 4 – tee; No. 5,6 – cross):
 1 – pressure gauge; 2 – closing device; 3 – tee; 4 – pipe head conductor; 5 – throttle; 6 – four-neck 7 – flange.

To check the serviceability of the spindle wedge and the valve, it is necessary to open and close the valve 2–3 times with the force of one worker; the force for the initial opening and closing to failure should not exceed the power of two workers [2].

Rotation of the handle lever must be performed without the use of long sleeves. In these operations, wear of the wedge and spindle must not be allowed.

When operating the fountain fittings, any of the valves must be in full working order; they must be opened and closed.

The lever should open and close the valve as quickly as possible evenly and without reset. In this case, you cannot use auxiliary devices. If defects are found, they must be corrected while the valve is not under pressure.

Fig. 2. Christmas tree AF6aB-80/50X700K2:

1 – adjustable throttle; 2 – valve with automatic control of ZMADP; 3 – valve; 4, 5, 8 and 12 – valves with manual control ZMAD; 6, 10 – crosspieces; 7 – valve with remote control ZMADP; 9 – transfer flange; 11 – suspension; 13 – distributor

When operating a well, the upper drain line of the tree is always used as a working line, and the lower injection line is used when replacing a working fitting, or when parts fail due to wear and tear located above the spare line.

When moving from a working line to a spare line and vice versa, the following work is performed:

- you need to simultaneously and evenly open the valves on one line and close them on the other;
- use only end valves;
- use the lower (first from the barrel) spare valve only if the working valve (second from the barrel) located on the working line is faulty.

All valves of the fountain tree must be fully open during normal operating hours, except for the second valve from the trunk located on the operating line. When sand is not detected in the oil, you can close the valves located above the drain line.

The valve located in the lowest shaft can be used only in extreme cases, when it is necessary to urgently close the wells.

Responsibility for the serviceability of the equipment in the well lies with the production foreman, field mechanic and, in shift mode, the senior shift foreman.

The senior operator monitors equipment, bolted connections on valves, manifolds and valves. In critical wells, monitoring and inspection is carried out very strictly.

Leaks at valves and manifold connections must be repaired as a matter of urgency. Leaks should be reported to the foreman or field mechanic. Surface scheduled preventive maintenance of wellhead equipment must be carried out simultaneously with underground equipment.

During the operation of flowing compressor wells, a large amount of sand and gas media with oil comes out, this greatly affects individual parts of equipment and injection lines; These parts wear out. Therefore, the master must know the characteristics of the main parts and have spare parts, such as tees, crosses, flanges, gas-kets, etc.

Analysis of the latest research and publications.

The flange bolts are not tightened too much with a wrench at first, and fastening should be done towards the crosspiece. When checking, the valves are fully opened and closed again until they fail. The rotation of the valve flywheel is performed without using a long maniver.

All tree valves must be fully open during normal operation; and the second one on the reserve flow line must be closed.

In the valve shaft, it is allowed to use the lowest valve if necessary to urgently close the well.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem. The influence of intense sand production has not yet been completely eliminated.

Fig 3. Wellhead and Christmas tree in real

Formulation of the goals of the article (statement of the problem). The main goal of the article is to increase the durability of valves and increase oil production.

Presentation of the main research material. All tree valves must be fully open during normal operation; and the second one on the reserve flow line must be closed.

In the valve shaft, it is allowed to use the lowest valve if necessary to urgently close the well.

If a leak occurs in the flange connection and is not immediately repaired, the well may openly flow.

In order to dismantle the Christmas tree and send it for repairs, you must first fill the wells with a weighted clay solution and plug it.

Conclusions

1. This article provided detailed information on the installation and operation of oil wells.

2. The fountain tree is assembled at a factory or in a field workshop according to standard schemes, checked for leaks, and then delivered to the well in assembled form.

3. To check the connections for leaks, perform the following operations:

- close the lower main and outer side valves on the discharge lines;

- fill the tree with water, or at low temperatures with light oil;

- carry out pressure testing of the tree for test pressure from the holes for the pressure gauge installed on the buffer and hold for 15 minutes.

4. If a leak occurs on the valve flange and if it is not repaired urgently, the well may switch to an open fountain.

5. To send the Xmas tree for repairs, you need to fill the wells with a clay sinter solution and plug them.

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